

Prevalence and Determinants of Substance Abuse among Indian Adolescents: A Review

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Abstract- This article explores the effects of substance misuse among adolescents in India. Substance abuse is an area of growing concern having a direct impact on the health of the people as well as an indirect impact on the social and economic status of the country. Over the time, substances are used in an unhealthy way to respond to various stress and anxiety among the people. Substance use among adolescents has been widely documented across the country. Numerous researchers have carried out different aspects of substance use such as initiation, prevention or intervention, pattern and prevalence, effects and implications and, knowledge- attitude mapping, etc. However, it is observed most of the studies focus on tobacco and alcohol use and: There is limited evidence on the extent of use of other substances among adolescents.

Keywords: Substance Abuse, Adolescents, Pattern, Prevalence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Substance abuse is a serious public health concern globally. In recent years, substance abuse has increased, and a higher prevalence of the use of addictive substances has been observed, specifically among youth and adolescents, them being. As they are the most vulnerable groups to substance abuse. Therefore, substance use among children and adolescents is considered as an urgent public health concern. According to WHO, Substance abuse refers to the harmful or hazardous use of psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs. One of the key impacts of illicit drug use on society is the negative health consequences experienced by its members. Drug use also puts a heavy financial burden on individuals, families and society (1).

During puberty, the young people pass through transitional states in different aspects such as physical, mental, psychological, and emotional. A shift in emotional and mental regulation builds up risky behaviors including substance use at an early age. It is reported that the first initiation of substances usually takes place during this period and it continues to the later stages of life in many people. Use of illegal drugs, alcohol, tobacco, misuse of prescription drugs, etc, poses various health problems, including substance use disorder (SUD)

and other serious psychological distress. Various research studies are carried out on the pattern and prevalence of use of different psychoactive substances.

It is not much bewildering as it is well known that adolescent this stage is the period of experimentation, exploration, risk-taking, and independence carving, and all these behaviors are quite related to substance misuse. Therefore, the incidence of substance use is becoming higher and increasing slowly during this period. It is noted that early use of drugs increases a person's chances of becoming addicted. At this juncture, the role of prevention and early intervention is appropriate strategy to control substance abuse.

II. METHOD

This article is a narrative review focusing on studies conducted in India which were published from 2009-2019. We accessed scientific articles and reports published during the last two decades on adolescent substance use. In total, 130 articles were reviewed, and 10 articles were included in the study. For this overview, the adolescent population was defined as aged 11–19 years; however, since many reviews targeted youth (aged 15–24 years) along with adolescents, exceptions were made to include

reviews targeting adolescents and youth. We did not apply any limitations on the starting search date or geographical settings.

A broad search strategy was used that included a combination of appropriate keywords, medical subject heading, and free text terms. The search was conducted using search engines such as Pub Med (NCBI), Embase (Elsevier), Web of Science (Clarivate), Scopus (Elsevier), and Google Scholar. Government reports and policies were accessed through the websites of various ministries of the Govt. of India. These articles provide information about the consumed drug type, its prevalence of use in terms of sex and age, and the experiences of adolescents with at least once consumption in the adolescent's life. Some articles had only pointed only to drug consumption, which was also included in this research.

II. RESULTS

The prevalence of drug consumption: Studies from India

A good number of studies are carried out by Government and Non-Government organizations on the prevalence and patterns of substance abuse in India. However, these are targeting the general population, including adolescents. Very few studies are done specifically on adolescent age groups across the country. Some of these selected research studies are given below:

A cross-sectional study was conducted to identify the prevalence of substance abuse and its pattern among adolescents in rural and urban communities of Surendranagar district, Gujarat with 300 rural and 300 urban adolescents' sample. Results of the study showed that the prevalence of substance abuse was 30.17 per cent in total, while adolescents from the rural community had a higher prevalence of 37.67 per cent. Prevalence of substance use was significantly higher in males, 55.33 per cent compared to females, 5 per cent.

Tobacco was the most common substance abused by the adolescents in this study. The study concluded that the prevalence of substance abuse was higher in

rural compared to urban communities and in males as compared to females. Chewing form of tobacco is the most common form of abusing tobacco followed by smoking (2).

A cross-sectional study was conducted on the prevalence, patterns and profile of adolescent tobacco users in Bhubaneswar City, Odisha with 906 subject samples. About 9.9 per cent of students from private colleges reported using smokeless tobacco whereas 10 per cent of students from government colleges used chewing tobacco. However, about 17 per cent of males and 5 per cent of females reported having ever tried smoking. The responses of the study subjects on their belief that tobacco companies try to lure young people to use tobacco products by 54.7 per cent of males, and 45.3 per cent of females as reported (3).

Effects of Substance Abuse

A cross-sectional study was conducted on the prevalence and pattern of psychoactive substance use among late female adolescent students aged 18-25 years in universities of Chandigarh, North India. In the study, the lifetime prevalence of psychoactive substance use was 13.6 per cent. Participants reported the causes of use were; out of curiosity, for having fun, personal problems, easy availability, and familial use. About 52.9 per cent of students reported their using it within the last 3 months; out of among them, some were having had health problems. Association of psychoactive substance use was significant for age, socioeconomic status and family history. It is also revealed by the researcher that, due to the sensitive nature of reporting substance use, the lifetime prevalence of 13.6 per cent among female young students may be an under estimation(4).

Another study reported an epidemiology of alcohol consumption in an urban area of the Kancheepuram district, Tamil Nadu among late adolescents. The result of the study cited the prevalence of alcohol consumption among the study participant's was found to be 39 per cent. The major determinants of alcohol consumption which were found to be statistically significant, were those belonging to a nuclear family, with consumption of alcohol by

family members, those who did not receive advice regarding harmful effects of alcohol from family members, those having stigma of being a non-drinker among friends or /peers and those having no awareness of health problems caused due to alcohol consumption. The study revealed that it is high time to change the approach to educating the younger generation about the effects of alcohol consumption by intensive behavioral change continuum activities coupled with encouraging refusal skills to overcome peer pressure(5).

The consumption prevalence for each drug type in different cities

A cross-sectional study was conducted on the prevalence and pattern of alcohol consumption using alcohol use disorder identification tests among students at a medical college in Goa. The results showed that the prevalence of alcohol consumption was found to be 39.4 per cent. Alcohol prevalence among females was higher (40.6 per cent) compared to males (38 per cent). Among the alcohol consumers, 82.3 per cent were light drinkers while 17.7 per cent were identified as heavy drinkers. Hazardous alcohol consumption was identified in 46.7 per cent of alcohol consumers. About 20.9 per cent of alcohol consumers showed signs of alcohol dependence. The causes of alcohol use were due to stress, lack of awareness of the ill effects of alcohol consumption and peer pressure. Counseling to deal with stress related to academic studies and negotiating peer pressure should be provided (6).

A study to assess the prevalence and pattern of substance use among male adolescents in suburban areas of Delhi revealed that nearly more than half 55.6 percent of male adolescents use one or more substances in their lifetime. About 44.26 per cent of adolescents started to use substances before 13 years of age. The most common causes specified by the subjects to take substances were "to be liked by friends" 55.38 per cent, "to feel like an adult", 24.6 per cent, and, 13.11 per cent reported: "like the feeling of using substances". Common substances used by adolescents were any kind of tobacco (77.05 per cent), inhalants (26.23 per cent), and alcohol (11.47%). Most of the adolescents, such as 85.25 per cent, were getting different

substances from their friends and the rest of 14.25 per cent by themselves. More prevalence of substance use was seen among adolescents from a nuclear family (7).

Patterns of Substance Abuse across various parts in India

A cross-sectional study was conducted on the prevalence and pattern of substance abuse among school-going adolescents in a hilly district of the Himalayan region in India. It was reported that out of the total of 2864 participants, 27.4 per cent had indulged in substance abuse at least once in their lifetime. Prevalence of current and regular users was 13.8 per cent and 4.1 per cent respectively. Alcohol was the most commonly abused substance among every user 18.1 per cent followed by tobacco 17.6 per cent and cannabis, 6.2 per cent. Around 85 per cent of the students were answered that indulgence in substance abuse is harmful to health.

The research study also revealed that substance abuse and factors such as addiction among friends and family members, inability to spend quality time with parents, gender and the older age group of 16-19 years were the factors found to be positively associated with substance abuse. The Higher knowledge of participants about the deleterious effects of this problem did not translate into any beneficial behavioral change. It was suggested that life skill education focused on school-going adolescents is imperative, for this problem. Further, the negative influence of family abuse practices and the inability to spend quality time with their wards highlight the necessity to include parents in any awareness campaign being planned(8).

A cross-sectional study on the pattern of alcohol use among students in a medical College of Bareilly, North India was carried out. The study showed a variable pattern of drinking among the medical students. It was about 87.3 per cent for non-problem drinkers, 6.8 per cent of hazardous alcohol users, 2.3 per cent for harmful and 3.6 per cent for dependent users. It was revealed that parental behavior towards alcohol use has a significant impact on their children's behavior. Therefore, it is very clear that

parents' alcohol habits are a major determinant of children's drinking behavior (9).

A study on the prevalence and correlates of alcohol use among school-going adolescents in Kerala was carried out. A total sample of 7560 students in the age group 12-19 years from 73 schools were considered in this study. The overall prevalence of lifetime alcohol use among adolescents was 15 per cent (23.2 per cent among boys and 6.5 per cent among girls) and was increasing with age. About 25.3 per cent of students reported hazardous alcohol use. The prevalence of alcohol use was higher among students from urban areas and those with a part-time job. It was concluded that Alcohol use among adolescents in India deserves greater attention than it has previously received because it is started at an early yearly age, at 13.6 years as per the study and is associated with a range of negative mental health problems(10).

A study on prevalence and causes of substance abuse among undergraduate medical college students, in Odisha was carried out. This study showed that the prevalence of substance abuse was found to be 45.87 per cent and for males 74.03 per cent. Cigarette, most common substance of abuse was found to be 72 per cent followed by alcohol (68 per cent), gutkha (24 per cent) and drugs (23 per cent). Staying in a hostel, non-satisfactory intra-familial relationships curiosity about substances, academic and peer pressure, and family problems were the major initiating factors. It can be concluded that continuous use of these substances despite knowledge of their associated hazards reflected a lack of health consciousness and need for proper health education (11).

IV. DISCUSSION

Findings from several studies indicate that substance abuse is increasing in an alarming rate among the younger generation, particularly among children and adolescents. Most of the studies reported, a higher prevalence of substance use among urban adolescents, however, few studies revealed a different pattern of substance use in rural areas. For example, alcohol is more common among urban

adolescents while chewing forms of tobacco and country liquor among their rural counterparts. Gender is an important variable that determines the prevalence of drug use. Though most of the studies say the prevalence of alcohol and other drug use among girls is substantially lower than among boys, it is notable that alcohol use is increasing among girls particularly in the urban areas and also among adolescents. Most of the studies reported alcohol and tobacco are found to be most common in use and familial type of use among adolescents and younger people followed by gutkha, cannabis and other drugs. Cigarette smoking is found to be more common than the chewing form of tobacco.

V. CONCLUSION

One of the recent concerns in the field of adolescent education is substance misuse, as the first initiation of drugs, alcohol and tobacco usually starts from the adolescent age group. This habit creates both short-term and long-term impact that continues into adulthood and adversely affects young population at both individual and familial-societal level. Substance use among adolescents has been widely documented across the country. Numerous researches have studied different aspects of substance use such as initiation, prevention or intervention, pattern and prevalence, effects and implications, knowledge attitude mapping and more. However, it is observed most of the studies focus on tobacco and alcohol use. There is limited evidence on the extent of other substances use among adolescents.

It is also noticed that adolescents, most often enter into the world of substance misuse experimenting with tobacco, then transition to alcohol and further to hard drugs. Once this behavior is established or deep rooted, it is very difficult to change. Therefore, some research studies are needed to evaluate the strategies preventing this one-way transition path from tobacco to hard drugs. From the analysis of different research studies, the powerful influence of peers on adolescent substance misuse cannot be overlooked. Peer factors are responsible for early initiations of tobacco, alcohol and even some hard drugs. Besides peer factor, parental attitudes, and

behavior also influence substance misuse among young children. Table: Showing the results of selected studies

Citation(& Year of Publication)	Study Title	Population Age Group & Sample	Study Findings
Jasani et.al (2009)	Prevalence of substance abuse among adolescents of urban and rural community in Surendranagar district, Gujarat	Adolescents 300 Rural & 300 Urban	Prevalence of substance abuse 30.17 percent. Rural community has higher prevalence than Urban. Prevalence in male is significantly higher than female. Tobacco is the most common substance used.
Vir Kaur et.al (2019)	Prevalence and pattern of psychoactive substance use among female students aged 18-25 years in universities of North India	Adolescents/ youth female Chandigarh students(18-25)	Lifetime Prevalence of psychoactive substance. " Use of substances due to curiosity, fun, personal. Problem, early availability, familial use. Due to sensitive nature of reporting substance abuse. the lifetime prevalence of 13 percent may be an underestimation.
Yash Jairam Verenkar et.al (2018)	Prevalence and pattern of alcohol consumption using alcohol use disorder identification test among students at a medical college in Goa, India	Youth students of medical college	Prevalence of alcohol consumption 39.4 percent. Prevalence is higher in female than male. 82.2 percent of alcohol consumers showed sign of alcohol dependence.
Daniel et.al (2017)	A study to assess the prevalence and pattern of substance use among male adolescents in suburban area of Delhi	Male adolescents in suburban area. Sample Size 110	About 55.6 percent of reported to use one or more in their lifetime. "Most common causes peer pressure, feeling like adult. Tobacco use 77.05 percent. " Inhalant 26.23 percent. " Alcohol 11.47 percent
Devender Kumar et.al (2017)	Alcohol and other substance abuse among youth: an obvious but neglected scenario in Shimla city of Himachal Pradesh, India	School going adolescents. Sample Size: 2864	27.4 percent had indulged in substance abuse once in life time. "Alcohol: among ever users 18.1 percent. Tobacco: among ever users 17.6 percent. Cannabis: among ever users 6.2 percent
T S Jaisooriya et.al (2016)	Prevalence and correlates of alcohol use among adolescents attending school in Kerala, India	School going adolescents Sample Size: 7560.	Lifetime prevalence of alcohol 15 percent (23.02 percent among boys 6.5 percent among girls) Hazardous alcohol use 23.5 percent Prevalence of use increases with age. Prevalence is higher among urban students.
TombaChingtham et.al (2015)	Prevalence And Pattern Of Substance Abuse Among The Students Of Higher Secondary Schools	Young Adolescents (16-19 years)	Prevalence of substance use is more in middle age group (16 years) adolescents, that is 86.67 percent. Frequently used substance like tobacco 68.12 percent then alcohol 20 percent, cannabis 5percent About 6.8 percent students used inhalants like gas and aerosol. Middle aged adolescents are more curious to taste and have fun from the substances then higher aged adolescents
Arun Singh et.al (2015)	A Study on Patterns of Alcohol Use Using Audit among the college students in a Medical College of North India.	Medical college students	A variable pattern of alcohol use. Non problem drinkers 87.3 percent Hazardous alcohol users 6.8 percent Harmful users 2.3 percent Dependent users 3.6 percent Parental use of alcohol has significant impact on children's behaviour for alcohol use.

Adidela Praneeth Reddy et.al (2014)	A Study on prevalence and pattern of substance abuse among street children and adolescents in the state of Andhra Pradesh, India	Street Adolescents	Prevalence was high among age group of 12-14 years and dropped out adolescents 48 percent. Influence of peer pressure act as the major influencing factor.
Janeswar A et.al (2019)	Prevalence patterns and profile of adolescent tobacco users findings from a youth survey A cross-sectional study	Adolescents Sample Size :906	Boys use tobacco 4 times higher than girls About 9.9 percent of college students uses smokeless tobacco. 10 percent use chewing tobacco Most of them believe that Tobacco Company try to lure the young people.

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